

STUDY OF GROUNDWATER PROTECTION AND CONTAMINATION IN THE TERRITORIES OF THE MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE LANDFILLS AFTER RECULTIVATION

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ABSTRACT: One of the most important directions of the project "Clean Country" in Russia is the reclamation of municipal solid waste (MSW) landfills. In this paper, the main attention was focused on assessment of groundwater protection at landfills in the Moscow region, analysis of the groundwater composition changes in the key site, study of soils as a secondary source of groundwater contamination. It has been shown that in many study areas the groundwater protection is quite low, which requires additional measures to isolate waste disposal bowls. In the key site during the landfill operation, many contaminants entering to the aquifer with the filtrate led to significant groundwater contamination. After reclamation, the level of groundwater contamination decreased, but excesses of standards for a number of heavy metals were noted. In order to study soils as a secondary source of groundwater pollution, different forms of heavy metals were carried out. The aerotechnogenic soil pollution features and the composition of the mobile forms of chemical elements have been revealed. The combination of low protection of groundwater and a significant content of heavy metals mobile forms creates the danger of groundwater contamination even after landfill reclamation, which needs to develop the special water protection measures.

Key words: groundwater, contamination, municipal solid waste landfills, secondary source of contamination, groundwater protection

INTRODUCTION,

At present time in Russia within the framework of the national federal project "Clean Country," large-scale reclamation of municipal solid waste (MSW) landfills is being carried out, aimed at reducing the negative impact of accumulated environmental damage. The Moscow region is a leader in carrying out measures to close landfills that have reached their capacity and then rehabilitate them. At a significant number of sites a unique opportunity has been presented to study the features of spatio-temporal changes in contamination of the natural environment components in areas of the reclaimed MSW landfills.

However, stopping the landfills operation does not always lead to a solution to the problem of groundwater contamination. Over a certain period of time, contaminated leachate may enter from the landfill body; in addition, contaminated soils around the landfill may be a secondary source of groundwater contamination. A particularly hazardous situation can be observed in areas where aquifers are poorly protected (for example, in the areas of "hydrogeological windows").

According to authoritative researchers (Bozkurt et al., 2000), no coating can permanently prevent the penetration of atmospheric precipitation into the landfill body, since in the long term the coating will deteriorate and its barrier function may be impaired. Practical experience and scientific research have led to an understanding of the impossibility of creating "absolutely" safe technologies. In this case, it is necessary that the level of risk is acceptable.

Landfill leachate is characterized by high organic and inorganic contaminants concentrations, including highly toxic substances. We have studied on the basis of literature sources consideration the duration of metal leaching from landfill body, changes in their mobility under aerobic and anaerobic conditions and forms of binding in the solid phase (Galitskaya, et al., 2020), as well as a study of the duration of ammonium nitrogen entry into groundwater (Galitskaya, et al., 2021). It is concluded that the risk of metals entering into groundwater after the landfill closure is minimal. As distinguished from the metals the concentrations of another important component of the leachate - ammonium nitrogen - remain very high for a long period. The duration of ammonium nitrogen contamination of the leachate is one of the most acute problems in landfills, and it is likely that its presence will determine when the landfill becomes stable and monitoring can be completed after landfill closure (Price, et al., 2003).

However the contaminants accumulation in the soil near the landfill sites and adjacent territories can lead to the formation of a secondary source of contamination. Under changed conditions after the landfill reclamation, the chemical elements contained in the soils in mobile forms can enter the aquifer

with infiltrating waters, which can lead to groundwater contamination. In addition, contaminated soils can affect on human health while dusting.

Study of contaminated soils was conducted at a number of municipal solid waste landfills in the Moscow region (Galitskaya, et al., 2022). To assess the hazard of the vadose zone as a secondary source of groundwater contamination, an approach was used that consists in calculating moisture and mass transfer in the vadose zone using the WHI UnSat Suite Plus 2.2.0.2 software package. This allowed evaluating both changes in the bulk content of contaminants in soils. But to understand the impact of pollution entering the aquifer better, at the next stage it was necessary to find out the forms of occurrence of metals in soils and determine the mobility of metals.

In this paper, the main attention was focused on the following aspects: 1 - assessment of the groundwater protection in the reclaimed MSW landfills; 2 - analysis of changes in the composition of groundwater in the key site; 3 - study of soils as a secondary source of groundwater contamination.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Materials of engineering geological and ecological survey conducted by various organizations at a number of MSW landfills in the Moscow region were used to solve the tasks.

To assess the groundwater protection seventeen MSW landfills located in the Moscow region and subject to reclamation, were examined. The term "protection" is used in Russia to characterize the degree of isolation of groundwater from surface pollution. Protection is controlled by the time it takes for pollution to penetrate from the surface of the earth into the aquifer. Seven landfills are located on alluvial soils, represented by sands of various sizes, the remaining landfills are located on moraine loams with sand layers. A quantitative assessment of groundwater protection was carried out using the method, according to which the time of contaminants reaching the unconfined aquifer level is determined (Goldberg, 1987).

The MSW landfill "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" was chosen as the main object to study the changes in the groundwater composition and the soils as a secondary source of groundwater contamination/ Additionally, when studying soils the modernization MSW landfill "Timokhovo" was considered.

When assessing groundwater contamination maximum permissible concentration in drinking water (MPCd) were used. In addition, since the rivers in the area of the landfill location are of fishery importance, in order to assess the potential hazard of groundwater as sources of surface water pollution, a comparison was also carried out with the maximum permissible concentration in the waters of fishery significance (MPCf). The MPC exceedances are presented in the form of generalized associations. In the association of contaminants: Ph - phenol, Oil - oil products, the number to the right of the element is the concentration coefficient equal to the ratio of the contaminant concentration in groundwater to MPCd or MPCf.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Groundwater protection

As the results obtained showed, the lowest levels of protection of the first aquifer from the surface in Quaternary sediments are typical when landfills are located in alluvial sands. In addition, during the landfill operation, a gradual rise in the groundwater level was observed at all landfills, and the flooding of the territory and the formation of a local technogenic aquifer occurred in the sites composed of relatively poorly permeable soils.

The aquifers in pre-Quaternary deposits are characterized by higher protection (with the exception of areas where hydrogeological windows occur). However, to obtain more accurate estimates, a more detailed study of the hydrogeological section is necessary due to the significant heterogeneity of sediments. For example, heterogeneity is characteristic of moraine loams, usually considered as low-permeability rocks, but in which in a number of areas there are a large number of sand layers, and it significantly increases their permeability.

Thus, in many areas being reclaimed and reconstructed in the Moscow region, the protection of groundwater from surface contamination is quite low, which is due both to the lack of appropriate standards for the placement of old landfills, and to the rise in groundwater levels during their operation. Accordingly, this determines the need to take additional measures to isolate waste disposal bowls. When assessing the protection of both unconfined and confined groundwater, systematic errors may arise associated with the selection of input values for the filtration properties of sediments, which can vary significantly with their heterogeneous structure.

When reclaiming or modernizing landfills, in some cases landfill deposits are moved. It is important to know the groundwater protection in the nearby territories. Based on the calculations performed, maps illustrating the protection of groundwater from surface contamination were constructed. Various geostatistical methods were employed for the creation of these maps implemented using Golden Software Surfer.

The most accurate and reliable results were obtained using kriging and inverse distance weighting (IDW) methods. The application of these methods was justified by the limited number of point data, where alternative geostatistical approaches resulted in significant gaps and artifacts, thereby reducing the quality of spatial modeling.

Thus, in the studied areas in the Moscow region, the protection of groundwater is quite low and additional measures are required to isolate waste disposal bowls. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the gradual rise in groundwater levels and flooding of the territory. An increase in groundwater levels is caused by watering of rocks and the development of such a geological process as technogenic regressive lithogenesis. In the process of technogenic regressive technogenesis, significant chemical and mineralogical transformations of rocks occur, such as, for example, the removal of soluble salts, changes in the exchange complex, gibbsitization of clay minerals, kaolinitization of hydromica, montmorillonite, etc. This, in turn, leads to a change in the state and engineering-geological properties of rocks, a change in the filtration properties of rocks is observed.

Groundwater contamination at the site of MSW landfill location

The MSW landfill "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" is located in the north-west of the Moscow region. The landfill had been in operation for more than 60 years. In 2020, the reclamation of the landfill was completed. In the geological structure up to the depth of 40 m, upper-mid-quadernary alluvial-fluvioglacial and mid-quadernary moraine deposits, overlain from above by technogenic soils take part. The bedrock deposits are represented by: Lower Cretaceous (K₁) sandy clays, Upper Jurassic (J₃) black clays, Upper Carboniferous (C₃) white fractured limestone.

Hydrogeological conditions are characterized by the presence of unconfined aquifer in technogenic deposits and middle-upper quadernary alluvial-fluvioglacial sands. Moraine loams with a thickness of about 20 m serve as an aquitard. The aquifer is recharged by atmospheric and surface waters. The discharge of the aquifer occurs in the Volga River and its tributaries (the Dubna, the Sister and the Black River), as well as in the Moscow Canal. The Upper carboniferous artesian aquifer is separated from the unconfined aquifer by a layer of Jurassic clays of considerable thickness, which implies its good protection.

The study of the chemical composition of groundwater before reclamation showed the following results.

The groundwater sampled from the aquifer under the landfill body was characterized by neutral pH value of 7.61, mineralization (dry residue) – 2.2 g/dm³, total hardness – 7.33 mg-eq/dm³, permanganate oxidizability > 100 mg/dm³, dissolved oxygen content – 3.1 mg/dm³. The associations of the contaminants are: Oil (6.6) Cr(2.0) Ni(1.7) Cl(> 1.4) – according to MPCd, Ph(82) Oil(13.2) Mn(9.5) NO₂(9.0) Zn(6.3) Cl(> 5) Cr(5.0) Fe(3.9) Ni(3.4) Sr(1.3) – according to the MPCf¹.

The groundwater sampled from the well located outside of the bypass ditch was characterized by neutral pH value of 7.67, mineralization (dry residue) – 1.9 g/dm³, total hardness – 6.43 mg-eq/dm³, dissolved oxygen content – 5.3 mg/dm³, permanganate oxidizability – 68.4 mg/dm³. The associations of the contaminants are: Mn(20.5) Ni(2.8) F(2.7) Fe (1.4) Cl(> 1.4) – according to MPCd, Ph(270) Mn(205) NO₂(61.5) Cu(13) Zn(7.7) Ni(5.7) Cl(>5) Fe(4.2) Sr(1.9) SO₄(1.6) Cr(1.3) Oil(1.2) – according to MPCf.

The groundwater sampled from the well at a distance of 200 m from the landfill was characterized by neutral pH value of 7.51, mineralization (dry residue) – 2.8 g/dm³, total hardness >50 mg-eq/dm³, dissolved oxygen content – 6.1 mg/dm³, permanganate oxidizability – 2.28 mg/dm³. The association of the contaminants is: Ph(16) Zn(2.6) Cr(1.2) – according to MPCd. No exceedances of MPCf were detected.

The entry into the aquifer a number of contaminants (phenols, oil products, copper, cadmium, zinc, nickel, iron, strontium, chromium, chlorides, nitrites, sulfates, etc.) with the leachate has led to significant groundwater contamination, especially in comparison with the standards for water of fishery importance. Unfortunately, the limited number of observation wells and the lack of accurate data on the

¹ The number in brackets to the right of the element is the concentration coefficient equal to the ratio of the contaminant concentration in groundwater to MPCd or MPCf.

concentration of chloride and ammonium ions in the leachate and groundwater did not allow us to get a complete picture of hydrogeochemical situation.

Based on the analysis of the dissolved oxygen content, COD values, calculated Eh values in the leachate, as well as the results of gas-geochemical survey, it was found that at the time of the study, the landfill body was in anaerobic conditions, in some areas - in the phase of acetogenesis, in others - in the phase of active methanogenesis. Since at the time of the study, the decomposition of waste was going through an anaerobic stage in the phases of acetogenesis and active methanogenesis, it was assumed that the most intensive release of heavy metals from the landfill body had already occurred, and a process of attenuation was observed during the period under review. The following ways of heavy metals entering groundwater are potentially possible: 1 - with landfill leachate, 2 - with the reduction of previously deposited iron hydroxides and the transfer of metals sorbed on them to groundwater.

The study of the chemical composition of groundwater conducted in two years after reclamation based on municipal contract No. 2178501 showed the following results. Groundwater sampling was carried out at four points located along the perimeter of the test site - in the south, east, north, and west. Indicators of total mineralization (dry residue) vary within the normal range - 921-1037 mg/dm³. The BOD value in the selected samples was 1.79-2.41 mgO₂/dm³. The COD value in water was 31-38 mg/dm³.

The associations of the contaminants are:

Fe (7.0-9.3) Cd(1.3-1.8) Pb(1.4-1.7) Ni(1.1-1.2) - according to MPCd,

Ph(32-45) Cu(26-130) Fe (19-28) Pb(2.2-2.8) Ni(1.2-2.3) Zn(1.1-1.4) - according to MPCf.

After reclamation, the level of groundwater contamination decreased, but excesses of standards for a number of heavy metals were noted. It should be noted that an increased content of heavy metals in groundwater relative to the standards was noted in samples taken in the western and southern parts of the study area, that is caused by the groundwater flow direction to the southern and western parts of the territory. But nickel content was high also in the eastern part. It is possible that groundwater contamination with metals was also influenced by the enter of polluting components from soils due to atmospheric precipitation infiltrating.

Study the forms of heavy metals occurrence in soils

In order to study soils as a secondary source of groundwater contamination in the territories of the MSW landfills "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" and "Timokhovo", soil samples were taken and chemical-analytical studies were carried out, including the determination total composition of elements (decomposition by sintering followed by acid decomposition), and also the forms of metal occurrence using the method of extracts - aqueous, ammonium acetate and nitrate.

Based on the results of the analysis, the following groups of element fixation were identified: 1 - water-soluble, 2 - easily mobile (extracted with an acetate-ammonia buffer solution), including mainly exchange-sorbed forms (carbonate, sulfate and water-soluble forms could also pass into the extract, however, as shown the results of previous studies, their proportions are mainly insignificant), 3 - acid-soluble, allowing to assess the level of technogenic contamination of soils.

The results of the studies showed the following.

At the MSW landfill "Timokhovo", excesses of the MPC in the soils around the landfill were observed for arsenic (1.5-3.2 MPC) in all samples and nickel in one area (1.4 MPC). Exceeding the MPC for mobile forms was detected only in one area for copper (1.2 MPC). The percentage of mobile forms of elements from their total content averaged (%): water-soluble / exchangeable / acid-soluble - Co - 0.1-0.3/2-19/8-40, Ni - 0.1-0.2/ 2-9/5-22, Cu - 0.1-0.4/1-11/29-53, Zn - 0.1-0.4/9-18/12-39, As - 0.1-0.5/1-5/4-22, Cd - 0.1-0.3/ 19-39/34-58, Pb - 0.01-0.1/ 16-28/57-66.

At the MSW landfill "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" excesses of the MPC in the soils around the landfill were recorded for nickel (1.2-2.7 MPC), copper (1.1-12 MPC), arsenic (1.0-2.0 MPC) and in one site for zinc (13 MPC) and cadmium (3.1 MPC). Exceeding the MPC for mobile forms was detected in one area for zinc (6 MPC). The percentage of mobile forms of elements from their total content averaged (%): water-soluble / exchangeable / acid-soluble - Co - 0.2-0.7/3-12/12-75, Ni - 0.1-0.6/ 1-4/8-63, Cu - 0.2-0.5/1/13-66, Zn - 0.1-0.2/4-19/14-77, As - 0.3-0, 7/1-2/6-15, Cd - 0.1-0.2/ 13-28/26-73, Pb - 0.003-0.2/ 5-20/48-65.

In general, the intensity of soil contamination, the quantitative and qualitative composition of the forms of occurrence of elements vary significantly in different areas around landfills. In the study areas, aerotechnogenic soil contamination at the MSW landfill "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" is higher and the composition of elements exceeding the MPC is more diverse (Ni, Cu, As, Pb), despite the fact that the dimensions of the modernized MSW landfill "Timokhovo" are significantly larger (this is the largest testing ground in Europe). The noted differences are apparently associated not only with the influence of the

landfill and the wind rose, but also with the specifics of the soil and vegetation cover (presence of forest, arable, wetlands, etc. areas) in the adjacent territories.

Significant percentages of exchangeable forms of Co, Zn, Cd, Pb ("Timokhovo"/"Dubna" MSW landfills: Co – up to 19/12, Ni – up to 9/4, Cu – up to 11/1, Zn – up to 18/19, As – up to 5/2, Cd – up to 39/28, Pb – up to 28/20) are due to the high ability of soils in a number of areas to form sorbed forms, and acid-soluble forms ("Timokhovo"/"Dubna" MSW landfills: Co – up to 40 /75, Ni – up to 22/63, Cu – up to 53/66, Zn – up to 39/77, As – up to 22/15, Cd – up to 58/73, Pb – up to 66/65) indicate a high level of technogenic soil pollution, since in background soils the content of acid-soluble forms of these elements usually does not exceed 1-5% of their total content.

CONCLUSION

In the territories of many reclaimed and reconstructed MSW landfills in the Moscow region, the protection of groundwater from surface contamination is quite low, which is due both to the lack of appropriate standards for the placement of old landfills, and to the rise in groundwater levels during their operation. Therefore the additional measures are required to isolate waste disposal bowls. When assessing the protection of both groundwater and pressure waters, systematic errors may arise associated with the selection of input values for the filtration properties of soils, which can vary significantly with the heterogeneous structure of sediments. To obtain more accurate estimates, a more detailed study of the hydrogeological section is necessary due to the significant heterogeneity of sediments.

The results of study of groundwater chemistry changes in the key site (MSW landfills "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya") showed that the entry into the aquifer a number of contaminants (phenols, oil products, copper, cadmium, zinc, nickel, iron, strontium, chromium, chlorides, nitrites, sulfates, etc.) with the leachate during the landfill operation had led to significant groundwater contamination. After the recultivation, the level of groundwater contamination decreased, but excesses of standards for a number of heavy metals were noted.

The study of the forms of metal occurrence in the soils in the vicinity of MSW landfills "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" and Timokhovo" showed that the intensity of soil contamination, the quantitative and qualitative composition of the chemical elements occurrence forms vary significantly in different sites. Aerotechnogenic soil contamination at the MSW landfill "Dubna Pravoberezhnaya" is higher and the composition of elements exceeding the MPC is more diverse (Ni, Cu, As, Pb), despite the fact that the dimensions of the modernized MSW landfill "Timokhovo" are significantly larger (this is the largest MSW landfill in Europe). The noted differences are associated with the impact of the landfill body, the wind rose, the specifics of the soil and vegetation cover in the study territories. Significant percentages of the exchangeable forms of Co, Zn, Cd, Pb are due to the high ability of soils in a number of sites to form sorbed forms, and acid-soluble forms indicate a high level of technogenic soil contamination, since in background soils the content of acid-soluble forms of these elements usually does not exceed 1-5% of their total content.

The low groundwater protection from the surface contamination and a significant content of mobile forms of a number of chemical elements can create a hazard of groundwater contamination even after a landfill recultivation. It confirms the importance to conduct more detail research of engineering and geological conditions, the monitoring studies and also the development of environmental measures not only in the areas where the landfill body is located, but also in the adjacent territories.

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